

THE LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF SANOGENIC THINKING IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Through observation methods, it was possible to compare students' interactions, communication with peers, individual-psychological differences, to take into account changes in their behavior and existing problems, and to determine the ways of appropriate spiritual and educational influence. Among young students, they are provided with a set of activities that help them to develop their worldview, intellectual development, dynamics of thinking, independence in drawing conclusions, activity and their analysis.

Introduction. The processes of the lesson, out-of-class and auditorium activities in the higher education institution were chosen as the object of experimental work, and the results of the effect on this object were studied in the formative experiment-tests.

Indicators such as the homogeneity of the conditions created for all the general secondary education system during the period of the experiment (unified spiritual and educational work plan, University Regulations, teaching staff, information and technical support of the educational process), as well as the similarity of the composition of the control and experimental groups. taking into account that it was formed in the same proportion, the results in the control and experimental groups were compared only in terms of effective changes in educational work in 2023.

Literature review. In the study, the content and specifics of psychological training aimed at the development of sanogenic thinking among students at a higher educational institution were studied. The socio-psychological conditions, laws, methods, forms, tools and methods that serve to bring about a new qualitative stage of the experience were determined, and a system of necessary recommendations was developed based on the introduction to the experience of pedagogical practice.

In the course of research, psychological training was applied.

The composition of the methodology aimed at the development of sanogenic thinking among students at the higher educational institution was carried out as follows:
determination of the purpose, directions,

content and essence of experimental work; to ensure compatibility of experimental work with the subject of research; emphasizing the integrity, continuity, reliance on scientific-theoretical sources, its historicity, nationality, continuity and nationalism of the pedagogical process; taking into account the emotional, pedagogical and psychological characteristics and uniqueness of students; correctly defining the basis of experimental work and ensuring their relevance to the pedagogical goal; to ensure that the experimental work is based on facts, and the facts are accurate, scientifically based, historical, related to the topic, and derived from practice.

The level of sanogenic thinking of the students studying in institutions of higher education involved in stress experiments was studied. The results of the planned experimental work were compared and summarized. The results and conclusions were formalized in the form of a dissertation. In order to check the reliability and correctness of the results, a mathematical-statistical analysis was conducted based on the Student-Fisher criterion.

The purpose, tasks, periodicity, methods and tools, creation of necessary conditions, systematic organization of the formative experiment-test work ensured the effectiveness of the formative experiment-test, and the final stage guaranteed the effectiveness of the approval results and ensured its success.

Results and discussion. Mathematical-statistical analysis of the received numerical data was carried out based on the Student-Fisher criterion. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that the performance of the experimental group was higher than that of the control group, that is, it increased by 11.56%.

Based on the above statistical analysis, it can be said that psychological training aimed at the development of sanogenic thinking in students studying at a higher educational institution is the basis for the popularization of it, following the principles of systematicity, coherence, periodicity and representativeness.

In experimental research, the scales used to determine the order for the development of sanogenic thinking in students studying at a higher educational institution were used. From the collected information, a basis was created for determining the level of their spiritual growth, compliance with moral standards, healthy thinking. Based on the following formula, it was possible to determine one or another quality of the students, the level of education:

$$RR = \frac{\text{cumf} - f}{2} / N \cdot 100$$

In this case, R is the pre-determined rating for the person (from 0 to 34 points);

f-the number of subjects with the same descriptive characteristic;

cumf-cumulative frequency;

N- number of total participants to be diagnosed.

The principles of objectivity, reliability, and validity were used to determine the effectiveness of the methodology aimed at developing sanogenic thinking among students studying at a higher educational institution.

Through observation methods, it was possible to compare students' interactions, communication with peers, individual-psychological differences, to take into account changes in their behavior and existing problems, and to determine the ways of appropriate spiritual and educational influence. Among students, a set of activities was developed to help them develop their worldview, intellectual development, dynamics of thinking, independence in

drawing conclusions, activity and their analysis.

According to our experience, it is possible to determine the activity of entering the general educational and educational process, depending on the strength of mental stimulation in the central nervous system of young students.

A comprehensive plan of socio-psychological and educational activities aimed at the development of sanogenic thinking among the control and experimental groups was developed.

At the end of the experimental work, the dynamics of the development of sanogenic thinking among students in the experimental group was determined based on a number of criteria (Table 1)

Table 1.

The dynamics of the development of sanogenic thinking in young students (at the beginning of the experiment).

№	Criteria	I-level students			II-level students		
		high	medium	low	high	medium	low
1	Knowing the nature of moral categories	22	20	22	36	26	2
2	To have an understanding of legal norms	24	19	21	39	22	3
3	Compliance with rules and regulations in the community	21	21	22	34	25	5
4	Ability to perform public tasks in the auditorium	25	22	7	32	27	5
5	Ability to take the right path in conflict situations	23	19	22	35	22	7
6	To have the ability to understand fellow students, group members, to combine their interests with those of fellow students	20	23	21	37	20	7
7	Be able to demonstrate their interest in the partnership by showing that they are listening responsibly when their partner is expressing an opinion.	19	24	21	38	19	7
8	Being able to objectively evaluate their own activities, realizing their strengths and weaknesses	24	21	19	33	23	8
9	Being able to mobilize the will, to be able to calculate the possibilities of other people's needs	22	20	22	35	22	7
10	The degree of formation of national and universal values	18	23	23	34	20	10

11	Ability to take the right path in conflict situations	23	21	20	38	18	8
12	To have the ability to understand fellow students, group members, to combine their interests with those of fellow students	22	20	22	34	21	9
13	ability to overcome obstacles in the process of mutual communication	21	22	21	35	23	6
14	students' creativity, independence, striving for excellence, ability to develop educational and creative inclinations	19	25	20	37	20	7
Average:		22	21	21	35	22	7
In percentages:		34,4	32,8	32,8	54,7	34,4	10,9

Based on the results of the table above, it can be seen that the dynamics of developing sanogenic thinking among young students is higher in experimental groups.

Table 2 Indicators of the development of sanogenic thinking in young students

Groups	Number of students	Levels of growth of sanogenic thinking in student youth		
		High	Medium	Low
Experience group	965	503	383	79
Control group	900	302	302	296

As can be seen from the above table, the development of sanogenic thinking among young students depends on the formation of strong motivation in the educational process, mastery of educational work in combination with personal experience and knowledge.

Determining the mastery indicators and the number of students in the experimental group and the number of students in the control group using Yjnj, respectively, we get the following statistically grouped variation series, as well as the increase in moral categories and general cultural competence, the effectiveness of preventive measures with 4 points, legal literacy and the average effectiveness of legal culture was determined with 3 points, satisfactory educational activities with 2 points and unsatisfactory educational activities with 1 point.

From the table, it is possible to include the following designations on the indicators of the effectiveness of preventive measures and the indicators of the increase in legal literacy and legal culture among students.

Conclusions. Based on the obtained results, the level of effectiveness of the development of sanogenic thinking in students was analyzed mathematically and statistically, and the mean square deviation, sample variance, variation indicators, Student's selection criterion, degree of freedom based on this

criterion, Pearson's compatibility criterion and reliable deviations were found from the results found for the state at the end of the experiment.

A student should cover all aspects of the level of development of sanogenic thinking in young people (physical, mental, spiritual, educational level) and serve to continuously improve his skills.

Thus, the development of sanogenic thinking in young students is carried out in the following order: a model of social-psychological mechanisms of behavior is developed; the diagnostic object is selected; diagnostic methodology is defined (developed); Health care activities aimed at developing sanogenic thinking are carried out.

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